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Driving Growth: Fiscal Policy Strategies in Afghanistan

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ABSTRACT

The study mainly focuses on determining the relationship between fiscal policy and economic growth in Afghanistan. For this purpose, variables such as taxes, subsidies, inflation, and unemployment were selected to observe their impact on economic growth. Data were obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI) spanning from 1999 to 2023. Various econometric techniques including Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Robust Least Squares, and Granger Causality tests were employed to analyze the data. The results revealed a negative relationship between inflation and GDP, while subsidies and taxes showed a positive relationship with GDP. Additionally, unemployment exhibited a negative relationship with GDP. These findings suggest that to enhance economic growth in Afghanistan, efforts should be made to reduce the unemployment rate, while increasing taxes and subsidies.

Keywords: Fiscal policy; Economic growth; Taxes; Subsidies; Inflation; Unemployment; Afghanistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiscal policy can support human development and growth in various ways. These channels encompass both macroeconomic and microeconomic factors. The aim is to explore how these channels function in underdeveloped nations (Clements et al., 2004). Property taxes had a statistically negligible effect. The analysis suggests that economic and political authorities should reduce corporate and personal income taxes to boost economic growth in OECD countries. Additionally, they should increase indirect tax revenues to offset the decline in income tax revenues (Macek, 2014). There is a robust and favorable correlation between the increase in tax revenue, corporate income tax, and the expansion of gross domestic product (GDP). Moreover, there is only a limited correlation between the increase in GDP and social security and personal income taxes. It has been discovered that social security contributions and tax revenue growth have a major influence on GDP growth, but business and personal income taxes have little effect. It is interesting to note that social security contributions, which make up a smaller fraction of the tax base than personal income tax, have a greater impact on economic growth than the former, which is the primary tax form in the US tax system (Kalaš et al., 2017). Government grants play a crucial role in directing the growth and transformation of businesses. When companies are transitioning from traditional to new growth drivers, they must consider the green transformation conundrum (Liu et al., 2024). Innovation is what drives long-term, sustainable economic growth. The effect of government subsidies on firm innovation performance is becoming more widely acknowledged in industry, government, and academic circles (Ban et al., 2024). The short- and long-term effects of government spending on economic growth are favorable but not substantial. In contrast, taxes have a strong and favorable impact on economic growth in both time periods. Subsidies, on the other hand, have been shown to have a negative and substantial impact, suggesting that offering subsidies may have a detrimental short- and long-term effect on economic growth. Additionally, human capital also exhibits a negative and noteworthy influence, emphasizing the significance of investing in human resources to promote sustainable economic growth in Indonesia (Saragih et al., 2024).

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The connection between economic expansion and unemployment is crucial. The government should create efficient macroeconomic policies and ensure that the structure and operation of governance institutions are enhanced to stabilize economic growth and encourage job creation. Therefore, the government must provide a favorable climate and flexible labor market laws or legislation to attract numerous small firms and the private sector to expand employment and absorb a substantial population of unemployed individuals (Jamal et al., 2024). Based on the given discussions, the following research questions need to be answered, i.e.,

1. Does fiscal policy have an impact on economic growth?
2. Is there a positive or negative relationship between taxes and economic growth?
3. Is there a positive or negative relationship between subsidies and economic growth?
4. Will unemployment impact economic growth?

The study's objectives are as follows:

1. To analyze the impact of fiscal policy on economic growth in Afghanistan.
2. To investigate the relationship between unemployment and economic growth.
3. To examine the impact of subsidies and taxes on GDP in Afghanistan, and
4. To determine the relationship between inflation and GDP.

After the introduction section, the literature review is presented in section 2, followed by data and methodology in section 3. Results are presented in section 4. The final section concludes the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review is divided into different sub-sections, each of which holds its own importance in building knowledge. These sections discuss relevant literature to enhance understanding.

2.1: Literature Review on Fiscal Policy and Economic Growth

The following literature review is closed to the study's theme of investigation, i.e., Adebayo & Samour (2024) studied the effects of fiscal policy on the load capacity factor of BRICS countries using data from 1990 to 2018. They employed co-integration tests, second-generation unit root tests, and the unique panel nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag (PNARDL) approach. Their findings revealed that while greater use of renewable energy is linked to environmental sustainability, economic growth and non-renewable energy are the main contributors to environmental degradation. They suggested that governments of BRICS countries should use fiscal policy to promote ecological sustainability by increasing investment in renewable projects. Gara et al. (2024) examined the impact of fiscal policy on the economic expansion of Southeast European nations using data from 2010 to 2021. They analyzed social variables such as public debt, government effectiveness, fiscal freedom, rule of law index, and corruption. Various econometric models and techniques, including OLS, robust fixed and random effects models, and GMM, were utilized. Their findings suggested that fiscal policy tools contribute to the economic growth of Southeast European nations, with government efficiency, rule of law, and corruption levels playing significant roles. Asteriou et al. (2024) investigated the relationship between finance and growth empirically, focusing on financial depth, accessibility, and efficiency in 26 European Union nations from 1990 to 2020. Their findings revealed a significant relationship between finance-led growth and the stock market during normal times, but not during stressful times, such as the global financial crisis and the recent Covid-19 outbreak. Erdogan (2024) explored how green fiscal policies impact environmental sustainability from 1995 to 2020. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag approach and robustness checks, they found that environmental taxes are not effective in promoting green fiscal policy. Additionally, they highlighted the complexities surrounding the impact of energy innovation on environmental pollution.

Onoshole (2024) used dynamic Ordinary Least Squares techniques to assess the effects of fiscal policy on Nigeria's industrial sector from 1985 to 2022. They found evidence suggesting that higher total tax revenue to GDP ratios in high-income countries decrease the rate of return on investment and profit margin. Odili et al. (2024) examined how fiscal and monetary policies affect private sector investment in Nigeria from 2000 to 2020. Their findings indicated that real exchange rate, monetary policy rate, and outstanding balance of certificates of deposit had significant negative impacts on private sector investment. They also suggested reducing ongoing government spending. Oyedokun & Orenuga (2024) focused on the impact of financial stability on Nigeria's economic growth from 2002 to 2021. They found a statistically significant negative association between Return on Asset (ROA) and Nigerian economic growth. They concluded that proper financial management could boost Nigeria's economic expansion. Medee & Nenbee (2011) studied how fiscal policy variables affected Nigeria's economic growth from 1970 to 2009. They used error correcting mechanism techniques and Vector Auto Regression (VAR) methods. Their findings revealed a long-term equilibrium relationship between Nigeria's fiscal policy factors and economic growth. Daud (2023) investigated the relationship between digital technologies, financial inclusion, and economic expansion across 84 countries. Their findings indicated a positive and substantial impact of digital technology and financial inclusion on national economic growth. They suggested consolidating efforts to improve financial ecosystems through digital technology infrastructure.

2.2: Literature Review on Taxes and Economic Growth

Government taxes critical for attaining economic growth. Nam & Ryu (2024) investigated the impact of trade liberalization on ASEAN economic expansion, finding that high trade volumes and minimal trade barriers are correlated with trade openness. However, reducing trade barriers could negatively affect GDP in developing nations, suggesting that too much trade openness may hinder economic expansion. On the other hand, higher trade volumes have a positive impact on GDP, indicating potential benefits of trade openness for economic growth. Fang (2024) focused on the impact of income taxes, including both corporate and individual income taxes, on economic growth. Their findings suggested a negative correlation between the income tax rate and economic

growth rate. They emphasized the importance of considering the delayed impact of tax policies on economic growth and suggested further research and development in this area. Ağca et al. (2024) examined the macroeconomic activity and economic growth of Turkey using data from January 2006 to February 2022. They found that revenue from international trade and transactions significantly influences macroeconomic activity and economic growth. Their research highlighted the importance of considering different analytical approaches when studying such relationships. Ávila-López et al. (2024) explored the relationship between value-added tax (VAT) and economic growth in Mexico and China from 1991 to 2021. While the association between GDP and VAT was favorable in both countries, China exhibited a significant and positive relationship with VAT compared to Mexico. Mwiimbi & Phiri (2024) investigated the effect of direct taxes on Zambia's economic growth using quarterly data. They found that while Personal Income Tax and Withholding Tax had integrated order 1, Company Income Tax had no discernible impact on economic growth in the short or long term. David et al. (2024) examined the impact of tax income on the economic growth of Nigeria from 1991 to 2021. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique, they found that Value-Added Tax (VAT) and Personal Income Tax (PIT) had a negative influence on GDP, while Business Income Tax (CIT) showed a positive effect. Akbulaev (2024) analyzed tax types, tax receipts, and economic growth in Azerbaijan from 1991 to 2021 using time series techniques. They found a long-term cointegration relationship between tax revenues and economic growth. Nwaiwu (2024) empirically investigated the connection between Nigeria's economic growth and value-added tax. Their findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between input taxes and GDP, suggesting a strong relationship between value-added tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. They recommended diversifying Nigeria's monoproducer economy along taxation lines.

2.3: Literature Review on Subsidies and Economic Growth:

Government subsidies play a pivotal role in advancing economic growth of the countries. Liu & Xu (2024) examined the impact of government subsidies and subsidy continuity on the innovative performance of businesses using data from Chinese industrial enterprises. Their findings indicated that subsidized firms showed higher performance in Total Factor Productivity (TFP) and invested more in research and development compared to non-subsidized firms. Koorehpazan et al. (2024) investigated the effectiveness of an export subsidy scheme on the trading of walnuts and pistachios. Their findings demonstrated a significant and favorable impact of the export subsidy on the exported goods, suggesting its extension to new exporters to bolster the country's emerging industries. Han et al. (2024) compared the effects of distortionary taxes used to fund foreign direct investment (FDI) subsidies and examined their cross-country spillovers. They found that the optimal level and welfare gains of FDI subsidies depend on their funding sources, highlighting the importance of non-distortionary taxes for maximizing welfare gains. Pan et al. (2023) optimized renewable energy assistance policies by investigating the relationship between market competitiveness, government subsidies, and the Total Factor Productivity (TFP) of new energy firms. Their findings underscored the need for governments to examine these relationships to optimize renewable energy assistance policies amidst expanding energy demand and carbon neutrality restrictions. Rupasingha et al. (2023) examined the impact of the Broadband Initiatives Programme (BIP) on the labor market, finding a favorable impact on employment growth, particularly in start-ups and sectors related to information and communications technology. They highlighted the program's positive impact on employment, especially in metropolitan areas. Xue & Feng (2023) empirically analyzed the effects of government green subsidies on the risk of stock market meltdowns using data from Chinese A-share listed companies. Their findings revealed a significant negative relationship between the likelihood of stock market crashes and government green subsidies, providing insights for policymakers on evaluating the efficacy of green subsidies. Takahashi & Hashimoto (2023) investigated the impact of minor grants subsidies on the productivity of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Japan. They found that applicants experienced increased productivity and sales growth compared to non-applicants, particularly in post-entry companies operating in the service sector for six to ten years. They highlighted the positive impact of applying for subsidies with outside assistance on entrepreneurship and business expansion.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Economic growth is the dependent variable, while taxes, subsidies, unemployment, and inflation are the independent variables. The data for economic growth and the remaining variables are sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI, 2023). Table 1 presents all the dependent and independent variables, along with their symbols and units of analysis.

Table 1: List of Variables

Variables	Symbol	Unit
GDP growth	GDP	(Annual %)
Tax revenue	TAX	(% of GDP)
Subsidies	SBSD	(% of expense)
Unemployment	UEM	(% of total labour force)
Inflation	INFL	(Annual %)

Source: World Bank (2023).

The econometric techniques to be used include Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Robust Least Squares (RLS), outlier detection in the model, Granger causality test, ARDL Bound test, and long run analysis. OLS is a technique used to describe the relationship between an explained variable and one or more explanatory variables. It calculates the coefficients of the equation (1), where

$$\text{GDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{TAX}) + \beta_2 (\text{SBS}) + \beta_3 (\text{INFL}) + \beta_4 (\text{UEM}) + \mu \quad (1)$$

Robust Least Squares (RLS) is utilized when there are large errors or influential observations in the model. It serves as a proxy for the OLS method, aiming to mitigate the impact of outliers and accurately represent the data. Various robust techniques include M estimation, S estimation, and MM estimation:

1. M-estimation: Presented by Huber in 1973, M-estimation works to reduce large errors and detect outliers in dependent variables.
2. S-estimation: Presented by Rousseeuw and Yohai in 1984, S-estimation is a computationally intensive method used to detect outliers in independent variables.
3. MM estimation: Presented by Yohai in 1987, MM estimation detects outliers in both dependent and independent variables. It combines elements of both S and M estimation techniques.

The Granger Causality test examines the causal relationships between variables. It is a statistical hypothesis test to determine if one variable is useful in forecasting another.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the OLS estimates for ready reference. In the above table, the sign of coefficients indicates that inflation has a negative relationship (-0.486532) with GDP, subsidies have a positive relationship (1.103711) with GDP, taxes also have a positive relationship (0.361912) with GDP, while unemployment has a negative relationship with GDP (-6.128327). The R-squared value is 0.782493, indicating that 78% of the variation in the dependent variable GDP is explained by the independent variables. The F-statistic value of 17.98775 is very high, suggesting that the combined effects of the independent variables are significant in explaining the variation in the dependent variable.

Table 2: OLS Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	53.73851	10.04083	5.352001	0.0000
INF	-0.486532	0.226327	-2.149690	0.0440
SUB	1.103711	0.703688	1.568466	0.1325
TAX	0.361912	1.372199	0.263746	0.7947
UEM	-6.128327	1.148777	-5.334654	0.0000
Statistical Test				
R-squared	0.782493	Mean dependent var	3.362507	
Adjusted R-squared	0.738991	S.D. dependent var	10.53359	
F-statistic	17.98775	Durbin-Watson stat	2.040518	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000002			

Source: Author's estimate.

Table 3 shows the robust least squares regression estimates. The relationship between inflation (0.511) and taxes (5.119) with the dependent variable GDP is positive. Positive economic growth typically impacts inflation. However, inflation can have a detrimental effect on economic growth if it rises beyond a certain threshold (Hossin, 2015). Macroeconomic factors influencing a nation's economy include interest rates, exchange rates, inflation, and deficit financing. Bhat & Laskar (2016) found that there exists a positive correlation between inflation and GDP, and a negative association between GDP and interest rates during the study period in the context of Indian economy. In OECD nations, there is a statistically significant correlation between the increase in tax revenues and personal, corporate, and corporate income taxes, as well as gross domestic product (Đurović-Todorović et al., 2019). Direct tax accounted for 84% of real GDP, and there was a significant positive association between the two. Additionally, it was found that a one-unit increase in direct tax would considerably raise real GDP (Obura, 2022).

Table 3: Robust Least Squares Regression Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	8.501785	3.822268	2.224277	0.0261
INF	0.511527	0.091330	5.600875	0.0000
TAX	5.119461	0.584229	8.762766	0.0000
UEM	-5.264244	0.340281	-15.47028	0.0000
Robust Statistics				
R-squared	0.568703	Adjusted R-squared		0.507089
Scale	3.409316	Deviance		11.62344
Rn-squared statistic	316.9025	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)		0.000000

Source: Author's estimate.

The results also show a negative relationship between GDP and unemployment (-5.264). There exists a long-term negative correlation between GDP growth and unemployment, indicating that high GDP growth rates lead to lower unemployment (Haririan, 2010). Table 4 shows the Granger causality estimates for ready reference.

Table 4: Granger Causality Estimates

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
INF → GDP	23	5.09505	0.0176
GDP → INF		1.54287	0.2407
SUB → GDP	23	2.14295	0.1463
GDP → SUB		0.97859	0.3950
TAX → GDP	23	3.53926	0.0506
GDP → TAX		1.27561	0.3033
UEM → GDP	23	2.86633	0.0830
GDP → UEM		4.66810	0.0233
SUB → INF	23	2.58018	0.1035
INF → SUB		5.78957	0.0114
TAX → INF	23	4.91858	0.0198
INF → TAX		1.06704	0.3648
UEM → INF	23	1.62785	0.2240
INF → UEM		0.57908	0.5705
TAX → SUB	23	1.62277	0.2249
SUB → TAX		1.77317	0.1982
UEM → SUB	23	2.17059	0.1431
SUB → UEM		1.00145	0.3869
UEM → TAX	23	3.34634	0.0581
TAX → UEM		0.26271	0.7719

Source: Author's estimate.

The results confirmed the unidirectional causality running from inflation to economic growth, thereby confirming the inflation-led growth hypothesis in the country. Furthermore, government taxes Granger cause economic growth in the country. There is a bidirectional causal relationship between the unemployment rate and economic growth. Inflation Granger causes government subsidies, while taxes Granger cause inflation. Finally, unemployment Granger causes taxes in the country.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis demonstrates that fiscal policy, represented by subsidies and taxes, significantly impacts GDP in Afghanistan. Specifically, subsidies exhibit a positive relationship with GDP, indicating that government support in the form of subsidies contributes positively to economic growth. Similarly, taxes also show a positive relationship with GDP, suggesting that taxation policies play a role in stimulating economic growth. Moreover, the negative coefficient for unemployment (-6.128327) indicates that higher levels of unemployment correlate with lower GDP in Afghanistan. This underscores the importance of addressing unemployment through effective policy measures to promote economic growth and stability. Additionally, the positive coefficients for subsidies (1.103711) and taxes (0.361912) suggest that both subsidies and taxation policies have a positive impact on GDP. This implies that well-targeted subsidies and efficient tax policies can contribute to economic growth in Afghanistan. Furthermore, the negative coefficient for inflation (-0.486532) indicates that higher inflation rates correlate with lower GDP in Afghanistan. Controlling inflation is crucial for maintaining economic stability and sustainable growth.

In conclusion, the analysis highlights the significant impact of fiscal policy, subsidies, taxes, unemployment, and inflation on economic growth in Afghanistan. Effective fiscal policy measures, targeted subsidies, efficient taxation policies, and strategies to reduce unemployment and inflation are crucial for promoting sustainable economic growth and development in the country.

The following are the policy recommendations for the Afghan economy, i.e.,

1. Strengthening the economy of Afghanistan requires the adoption of well-developed fiscal policy, in which taxes and subsidies play crucial roles.
2. Controlling inflation is vital for sustaining economic growth. Therefore, while developing fiscal policy, measures to control inflation should be prioritized.
3. Reducing unemployment is crucial for promoting sustainable economic growth and development in the country. Creating more jobs and providing skills initiatives are necessary to improve the economy.
4. Government support in the form of subsidies contributes positively to economic growth, and taxation policies also play a role in stimulating economic growth. Increasing subsidies and providing more facilities to enhance exports can boost economic growth.
5. Reducing taxes can stimulate economic growth by giving consumers and businesses more money to spend on investments in initiatives that boost productivity and create jobs. Reduced taxes raise disposable income, encouraging economic growth and increasing consumer spending.
6. Changes in tax rates and government spending are two instruments used to encourage positive economic development. The government may attempt to boost economic activity when it slows down or deteriorates by lowering taxes or increasing spending on various government initiatives.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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